

Extraction-Photometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Vanadium with N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine

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N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine has been employed as a spectrophotometric reagent for vanadium(V) in presence of several metals. The influence of methyl and the resonance favouring methoxy substituents was studied, to determine their effect on complex formation. It was observed that a *p*-tolyl group at the hydroxylic nitrogen displayed both bathochromic and hyperchromic effects on vanadium complex whereas when present on azomethinenitrogen produced only bathochromic shift. The shift of absorption band to longer wavelengths is most pronounced when a *p*-anisyl group forms part of the conjugated system.

THE paper describes the development of a procedure for the extraction-spectrophotometric determination of vanadium with N-hydroxy N-*p*-tolyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine as the reagent. The complex is formed rapidly over a wide range of acidity and is stable for several days. This study also includes the synthesis of six hydroxyamidines and their colour reactions with vanadium.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical purity.

Synthesis: The reagents were prepared by the condensation of N-arylbenzimidoyl chlorides and N-arylhydroxylamines in absolute ether medium following the literature procedure.¹⁻³ These reagents along with the values of λ_{\max} and ϵ (1. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) of their vanadium complexes are listed below.

N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine; m.p., 163°; λ_{\max} , 560 nm (4210). N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-*p*-tolylbenzamidine; m.p., 190°; λ_{\max} , 575 nm (4200); N-hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-phenylbenzamidine; m.p., 174°; λ_{\max} , 575 nm (4460); N-hydroxy-N, N'-di-*p*-tolylbenzamidine; m.p., 156°; λ_{\max} , 578 nm (4335); N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-*p*-anisylbenzamidine; m.p., 170°; λ_{\max} , 580 nm (3950); N-hydroxy-N-*p*-tolyl-N'-*p*-anisylbenzamidine; m.p., 153°; λ_{\max} , 586 nm (4460).

The reagents are soluble in chloroform and moderately soluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate. A 0.1% (w/v) solution of the reagent in chloroform was employed for extraction work.

Vanadium solution: A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 0.567 g ammonium metavanadate (Hopkin & Williams) in double distilled water and diluting to the mark in a 250 ml volumetric flask. The amount of vanadium was determined volumetrically.⁴ From this stock solution, a solution containing 20 μ g of V ml⁻¹ was prepared.

Apparatus: All photometric measurements were made on a Carl Zeiss Universal Spectrophotometer VSU 1.

Colour development: An aliquot of the standard solution containing 100 μ g of vanadium was transferred to a 60 ml separatory funnel and 10 ml of glacial acetic acid was added. The solution was diluted to 25 ml with water. The colour was extracted using two 5 ml portions of the reagent solution and the organic phase was transferred to a 50 ml beaker. The chloroform extract was dried with anhydrous sodiumsulphate. The coloured solution was decanted into a 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted to mark. The absorption spectra of the vanadium complexes were recorded using chloroform blank.

Results and Discussion

The influence of *p*-tolyl and *p*-anisyl groups at the nitrogen atoms of the hydroxyamidine functional grouping were studied, to determine their effect on the spectral characteristics of the vanadium complexes. On the basis of the present study, the

following conclusions were drawn.

a. A *p*-tolyl group at either azomethine or hydroxylic nitrogen shifts the absorption band to longer wavelengths.

b. Resonance favouring *p*-anisyl substituent produces a significant bathochromic effect with a slightly reduced intensity.

c. The replacement of benzene ring by a *p*-tolyl group at the hydroxylic nitrogen has both hyperchromic and bathochromic effects.

N-Hydroxy-N-p-tolyl-N'-phenylbenzamide as a Reagent for Vanadium: The instantaneous blue-violet complex of the reagent with vanadium(V) has been utilized for the determination of the metal. The conditions were established after the following factors affecting the reaction were investigated.

Acid and Reagent concentration: Vanadium is quantitatively extracted from the aqueous phase by chloroform-reagent solution between 1.0 to 10.0 M acetic acid. For maximum colour development a 12 times molar excess of the reagent should be employed. Of the several solvents tried for extraction, chloroform was found to be the most suitable on the basis of high reagent solubility and extraction time.

Absorption spectra: The coloured system has a broad absorption maxima (λ_{max} , 575 nm) and the molar absorptivity of the colour reaction calculated on the basis of vanadium is about 4460 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. At the wavelength of maximum absorption linear calibration curves were obtained in the range 0.7

to 11.5 ppm vanadium/25ml, indicating that the method was suitable for vanadium determinations within this range. The practical range (Sandell's nomenclature) by this reagent is 2.0 to 8.5 ppm of the metal. The reagent is slightly more sensitive for vanadium than several other members of the hydroxyamides.

Divers ions—The complex is unaffected in the presence of iron, chromium, manganese, fluoride, borate and molybdate in concentrations 50-250 times that of vanadium. In the determination of 4.0 ppm of vanadium, the following ions do not interfere to the extents given in parentheses ($\mu\text{g/ml}$): Mn²⁺ (480); Fe³⁺ (1000); Cr³⁺ (400); Sb³⁺ (480); Zn²⁺ (600); Cu²⁺ (600); Ni²⁺ (400); Co²⁺ (600); UO²⁺ (500); MoO₄²⁻ (320); AsO₄³⁻ (600); F⁻ (240); PO₄³⁻ (400); B₄O₇²⁻ (200); SO₄²⁻ (1000); Cl⁻ (1200); NO₃⁻ (1000); tungsten(VI) and titanium(IV) seriously interfere.

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